

The Second Generation of Gods: How to Deal with a CLIL Didactic Unit

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ABSTRACT

Learning English is a fundamental requirement for the development of our students in the globalized world in which we live. Probably, the traditional methodology regarding to the teaching of foreign languages suffers, in some cases, a communicative component attractive enough to get the students to improve their competence in linguistic communication. That is why we propose the design of a didactic unit that uses the CLIL methodology, through the integration of language and content, to contribute not only to improve the foreign language, but also to reinforce content and cognitive skills. Activities are proposed with different execution patterns, from the 4Cs and progressively increasing the difficulty, both cognitive and linguistic level.

Keywords: CLIL, didactic unit, classical culture, multilingualism, cognitive skills

Introduction

According to Mehisto (2012: 15), “CLIL is a dual-focused teaching and learning approach in which the L1 (first language) and an additional language or two are used for promoting both content mastery and language acquisition to pre-defined levels”. It is a methodology based on integrated learning of content and foreign language. That is, CLIL teaching tries that the learning of a language is carried out of a natural way, motivating the students, and creating a context in which these can enjoy the learning of new contents at the same time as they practice and improve the language foreign object of learning.

Our aim has been to develop a didactic unit using CLIL methodology to aid both, teachers and students, to teach and to deal with a language in a natural way, while contents are reinforced. We

started with the content selection. So, we proposed a structure of a didactic unit following the four C's model (Coyle, 2007) related to the learning outcomes that our students would be able to achieve according to the teaching objectives. First, we decided to define curricular contents, that are those which are referred to the subject. Secondly, we set out cognition outcomes that can be defined as the critical skills that students use to understand and to cope with lesson contents. Thirdly, cultural contents through which students become aware that they are citizens of the world and that they understand their culture as well as other cultures. Finally, we described communication outcomes. If our aim is to encourage pupils to use the target language in a communicative way, in our unit should be planned not only vocabulary and structures for the topic, but also a language for interaction.

This unit is planned for Classical Culture, an optional subject in 3rd of CSE. It is named The second generation of gods. It is formed by six lessons and we are going to develop the first one. It will take us seven sessions. Throughout this lesson, the Bloom's taxonomy has been used to plan the different activities. We tried to design these by following the thinking skills what is supposed that our students should have achieved at the end of the unit, in order to reach the top of the pyramid. At the same time, we seek that the relationship between language and content developed during the lesson is related to the Cummins matrix, because our aim is that our students are able to go from the third quadrant (Low Linguistic Demands + High Cognitive Demands) to the fourth one (High Cognitive Demands + High Linguistic Demand).

We developed the first lesson and we included here the activities that were considered the most suitable for the topic. Everyone contains a table through it we tried to organize the task: subject, outline, thinking skills, language focus, language skills, time, level and preparation. After that, we suggested the steps to follow, the justification and the heading of the activity. Finally, we tried to connect the proposed activities with the Bloom's taxonomy (Anderson and Krathwohl, 2001) and the Cummins matrix (Cummins and Swain, 1996), taking into account not only thinking skills, but also communicative abilities.

The activities have been planned using different scaffolding tools (e.g. visual organizers, pictures, online games...) because we believe that these are absolutely essential in a CLIL methodology. If our aim is to engage students in the learning process, we have to make use of different educational tools to involve our pupils in their own development. In other words, we must provide them a multimodal input and we must plan the different tasks in different formats, if we want to achieve an effective communication (Meyer, 2010). To develop it, we have taken into account the ten criteria which seek to maintain the dual CLIL focus on content and language, according to Mehisto (2012):

- 1- make the learning intentions (language, content, learning skills) & process visible to students.
- 2- systematically foster academic language proficiency
- 3- foster learning skills development and learner autonomy
- 4- include self, peer and other types of formative assessment.
- 5- help create a safe learning environment.
- 6- foster cooperative learning.

7- seek ways of incorporating authentic language and authentic language use.

8- foster critical thinking.

9- foster cognitive fluency through scaffolding of

a) content,

b) language,

c) learning skills development helping student to reach well beyond what they could do on their own.

10- help to make learning meaningful.

That was done with the aim of ensure that our students acquire knowledges (content), skills (cognition), language (communication), social learning (culture) and key competences, and that all these are not replaced by only language (Nieto Moreno de Diezmas, 2018).

Unit Template

Unit: The second generation of gods	Area: Classical Culture	Lessons: 6	Ed. Level: 3rd CSE
Teaching Objectives	Final Task	Create a new Mount Olympus	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To raise learners' awareness of Olympian Gods To develop learners' abilities to classify gods' main facts To enable learners to distinguish a god and a hero To encourage students to learn with autonomy To make learners conscious of cultural differences To help learners to integrate different thinking skills 			
Assessment Criteria	Key Competences		
At the end of this unit, students will be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> identify the Olympians associate the different symbols and powers compare the god's and heroes' characteristics select information about the topic present a god's or hero's fact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Linguistic competence Digital competence Learning to learn Social and civic competencies Initiative and entrepreneurship Cultural awareness and expression 		
Materials Resources			
The Greek Gods: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eJCm8W5RZes http://www.theoi.com/greek-mythology/olympian-gods.html Quiz: https://b.socrative.com/teacher/#import-quiz/26011736 The weekdays: http://www.livescience.com/45432-days-of-the-week.html Activities: https://www.educaplay.com/es/recursoseducativos/2765094/the_Olympians_gods_power.htm https://quizlet.com/178564284/the-Olympians-flash-cards/ http://www.inspiration.com/go/ipad			

Content	Student Learning Outcomes	Cognition
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of the Olympians: gods and goddess in Greek and Rome • Symbols of the Olympian gods • The Olympians' powers • The Olympians' main facts • Heroes: the gods' relatives (Heracles, Perseus and Theseus) • The twelve labours of Heracles • Perseus and Medusa • Theseus and the Minotaur 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying the Olimpian gods and heroes • Associating the different gods' symbols to each one • Classifying the different gods' relationships • Comparing the god's characteristics • Selecting special information from general information • Designing a new god • Explaining gods' main facts • Listing the most famous heroes • Distinguishing a god and a hero 	
<p>Communication</p>	<p>Language for interaction</p>	<p>Language for the topic</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giving opinions: It's seems to me... In my opinion... • Agreeing: I agree, I see your point... • Disagreeing: I see your point, but... • Interrupting: Can I interrupt you for a second? • Summarizing: In a nutshell... • Rephrasing: In other words... • Asking for other's opinion: How do you feel about...? 		
<p style="text-align: center;">Vocabulary</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nouns: names of the gods, names of the gods' symbols, names of the heroes. • Adjectives: beautiful, handsome, bad-tempered, highest... • Verbs: overthrow, ride, spring... 		
<p style="text-align: center;">Structures</p> <p>Grammar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The present simple: rides, is... • The past perfect: married, were... • The pasive voice: are named, were known... • Prepositions: above, on, from, of... <p>Structures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The family relationships: Zeus' son... • Comparisons: Heracles is stronger than Perseus, Afrodite is more beautiful than Hera... • Descriptions: Cerberus has got three heads... • Questions: Who's the goddess of marriages? Where did the gods live? How did Theseus get out from labyrinth? 		
<p style="text-align: center;">Culture</p>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be aware of cultural differences: the names of the weekdays. • Get conscious about the myths' influence in western art: the birth of Venus, Saturn devouring his children... • Learn about etymology: myth, music, labyrinth... • Interact with peers. • Be able to do cooperative and collaborative tasks. 		

Lesson Template

Unit: The second generation of gods		Lesson: 1/6	
Content	Learning Outcomes		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation of the Olympians: gods and goddess • Symbols of the Olympian gods • The Olympians' powers 	Culture		
Cognition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be aware of cultural differences: the names of the weekdays • Interact with peers. • Be able to work in groups. 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying the Olympian gods • Associating the different gods' symbols to each one • Classifying the different gods' relationships • Comparing the god's characteristics • Distinguishing special information from general information • Designing a new god 	Communication		
<p>Vocabulary</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nouns: names of the gods, names of the gods' symbols. • Adjectives: beautiful, handsome, bad-tempered, highest... • Verbs: overthrow, ride, spring... <p>Grammar</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The present simple: rides, is... • The past perfect: were, called... • The pasive voice: are named, are known... • Prepositions: of... <p>Structures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The family relationships: Zeus' son... • Comparisons: Afrodite is more beautiful than Hera... • Descriptions: Cerberus has got three heads... 			
Students will be able:		Assessment Criteria	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to identify the Olympians • to associate the different symbols and powers, to compare god's characteristics • to classify god's relationships • to select information about the topic • to present a new god • to do a self-assessment and a peer-assessment 			
Material Resources			
<p>The Greek Gods: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eJcm8W5RZes</p> <p>The week days: http://www.livescience.com/45432-days-of-the-week.html</p> <p>Quiz: https://b.socrative.com/teacher/#import-quiz/26011736</p> <p>Activities:</p> <p>https://www.educaplay.com/es/recursoseducativos/2765094/the_Olympians_gods_power.htm</p> <p>http://www.inspiration.com/go/ipad</p> <p>https://quizlet.com/178564284/the-Olympians-flash-cards/</p>			

Activities

Introduction/Revision

1. Look at the pictures and answer the questions.

Warm up Activities

2. Do you know the Olympians? Start the quiz!

Main activities

3. Read the text and complete the grid. Write a sentence.
4. Complete the Gods' Family Tree. Explain it to your classmates using genitive saxon 's. Self-assessment activity.
5. Work in pairs. Describe the image to your partner. He has to guess the god or goddess.
6. Weekdays origin
7. In groups make a new god: main characteristics, relationship with the Olympians, power and symbol. Peer-assessment activity.

Reinforcement

8. Fill in the gaps with the correct word.
9. Make a quizlet of the Olympians.

Procedure and Activities

Introduction

This unit has been planned for Classical Culture, an optional subject in 3rd of CSE. This unit is named The second generation of gods. It is formed by six lessons and we are going to develop the first one, which will take us seven sessions.

The topic is addressed to twelve fifteen-year-old students who have chosen this subject.

Lesson Stages

Introduction

Activity 1

Subject	Classical Culture
Outline	Students have to look at two pictures and answer two questions to make a hypothesis about the topic.
Thinking Skills	Comparing and predicting
Language Focus	Giving opinion expressions
Language Skills	Speaking
Time	10'
Level	A1
Preparation	<p>The teacher gives to the students two pictures. After a couple of minutes, the teacher will write two questions on the blackboard and asks the students to answer them, using different samples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who is the character in the first picture? • What do you think both characters have in common? <p>The whole group will have to make a brainstorming.</p>

Steps to follow:

- Give students two pictures: Zeus and Thor.
- Write on the blackboard two questions.
- Students will be encouraged to answer these questions.
- Learners gather their ideas giving opinions
- Say the topic to the pupils.

Justification. This is an introductory activity whose purpose is to discover our pupils' language level, meanwhile we boost their curiosity about the topic. As a help, students are provided by some linguistic models below the pictures.

Heading: Look at the pictures and answer these questions. You can use the expressions in the box.

From: <https://www.flickr.com/photos/124561666@N02/14217863550>

From: https://es.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Archivo:Rome_Seated_Zeus.jpg

GIVING OPINION

It's seems to me that...

I've got the impression that...

In my opinion, both characters...

Warm up

Activity 2

Subject	Classical Culture
Outline	Students have to guess the names of different gods and their powers in a quiz.
Thinking Skills	Retrieving
Language Focus	None
Language Skills	Reading
Time	10'
Level	A1
Preparation	Students have to work with a laptop or a computer. The teacher gives them a code and everyone can access to a quizgame. That pupil with more correct answer in less time wins.

Steps to follow:

- Say the pupils they are going to create a game about the topic.
- Students switch on their computers or laptop.
- The page web is indicated to the learners.
- Give them the access code.

Justification: This is a warm up activity. Through to a game, we will achieve information about students' knowledge on this issue. It's a way of encouraging the teenagers to remain focused at the topic within a competition.

Heading: Do you know the Olympians? Start the [quiz!](#)

The screenshot shows a quiz interface with a blue header bar containing a logo, the username 'GLORIA8479', and a 'Menu' dropdown. Below the header is a pink bar with '1 of 8' and 'TEAM MAGENTA'. The main content area has a question: 'Who is the god of seas?' with four radio button options: A) Poseidon, B) Zeus, C) Apollo, and D) Hera. At the bottom is an orange 'SUBMIT ANSWER' button.

Main activities

Activity 3

Subject	Classical Culture
Outline	Students have to read a little text and see a video about the Olympians. Then they have to write a sentence following different patterns.
Thinking Skills	Identifying and associating
Language Focus	Special vocabulary about the topic. Possessive forms and preposition.
Language Skills	Reading, listening and writing
Time	25' + 45'
Level	A1
Preparation	The teacher delivers a sheet with a short text. After reading, it will be shown a video that continues with the topic. In a separate piece of paper, students have to complete a grid and to write sentences about the gods, using the possessive form (his/her) and the preposition of.

Steps to follow:

- Hand an introductory text to the students.
- Learners should read the text.
- After reading, a video will be shown.
- Give the pupils a grid with the god's name in the first column, the god's power in the second column and his power in the third column.
- Students have to complete the grid.
- Ask the learners to make sentences following the pattern given.

Justification: The first main activity is used as a topic presentation. It has two parts: a text and a video. First of all, students are provided with a text in which there will be passive voice structures and their explanation. Secondly, the new vocabulary will be introduced with synonymous. Finally, students will have a word bank at the end of the text. With this design we can scaffold student's learning process not only at the text level, but also at the sentences and words level.

In the second part of the activity, they will see a video. It will be used as a grammar reinforcement for possessive forms and as a knowledge of new vocabulary, through associating words and images.

The activity is planned in order that our students were able to identify the gods, their symbols and power and as well as to write correct sentences following a pattern.

Heading: Read the text. Do you want to know more about them? Click on the [video!](#)

THE TWELVE OLYMPIANS

The Olympian Gods

The twelve great gods of the Greeks **are known** as the Olympians, that is, **people call them so**. They **are named** from their **dwelling** or house. **Their name comes** from the Mount Olympus. Together they **preside** over every aspect of human life. They are a group who **rule** after the **overthrow** or destruction of the Titans. All the Olympians **are related** in some way, because they **are members of the same family**.

Text adapted from: http://www.desy.de/gna/interpedia/greek_myth/olympian.html

WORD BANK

Preside = Rule = To exercise authority = To govern

Video from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eJcm8W5RZes>

Now, complete the grid and write a sentence following the model.

The god's name	Power	His / Her Symbol
Zeus	Rain, thunder and order	Eagle
	Marriage, childbirths, empires and kings	Pomegranate
Aphrodite		Scallop shell
Hades	Underworld and death	
	Fire	Hammer
Poseidon		Trident
Artemis	Hunting	
	Music and poetry	Lyre
	War	Broze-tipped spear
Hermes		Winged sandals
Eros	Lustful love	
Athena		Owl
	Celebration	Cup of wine

SENTENCE MODEL

Zeus is the god of the rain, the thunder and the order. His symbol is the eagle

Activity 4

Subject	Classical Culture
Outline	Students have to complete the God's Family Tree.
Thinking Skills	Classifying and Applying
Language Focus	Special vocabulary about the topic. The Saxon genitive.
Language Skills	Writing and speaking
Time	45'
Level	A1
Preparation	The teacher gives an incomplete family tree to each group of three students. They have to complete it using inspiration maps . After that, students have to explain to the neighbor group the relationship between the different gods. When the activity is finished, the teacher shows to the class the complete family tree and students have to correct it with an assessment rubric.

Steps to follow:

- Put students in groups of three.
- Say the pupils they are going to do an online family tree.
- Students switch on their computers or laptop.
- The page web is indicated to the learners.
- After finishing the activity, the learners will be provided by the correct and complete family tree.
- Explain to the class that they have to do a self-assessment.
- Hand them the assessment table.
- The grid will be completed
- Collect the tables.

Justification. With this activity students are expected to be able to classify the gods' relationships using a visual organizer that helps to encourage them, and to deal with the Saxon genitive (e.g. Aphrodite's son). In addition, the use of IT tools fosters the learning process. At the end of the activity, they have to assess their knowledge through a formative assessment to help us understand how much and how well our learners are learning.

Heading: Complete the Gods' Family Tree. Explain it to your classmates using Saxon genitive: 's.

SENTENCE MODEL

Zeus is Poseidon's brother

Activity 5

Subject	Classical Culture
Outline	Students have to describe different images of gods to a partner who will have to guess it.
Thinking Skills	Describing and comparing.
Language Focus	Special vocabulary about the topic. Passive voice, present simple, adjectives and comparatives.
Language Skills	Speaking
Time	25'
Level	A1
Preparation	The teacher gives different images to the pupils in two sheets of paper (student A and student B). Then, he has to explain that we will work in pairs. While student A is describing his images, student B has to guess who is the god or goddess. And vice versa.

Steps to follow:

- Put the students in pairs.
- Learners are provided by a sheet of paper with different images.
- Images should be described to the partner and he has to guess the god's name.
- Go around each pair of students to assess their knowledge.
- The results will be put in a grid.

Justification. In this activity we will try to enhance our students' communicative abilities providing them a situation in which they can use the language in a natural way by interacting with a partner. To help them, they are supported by a structure box.

Heading:
Student A

Work in pairs. Describe the images to your partner. He has to guess the god or goddess.

STRUCTURE BOX

Dionysus is a **young** god. He has got **curly hair**. He is **younger / more intelligent than** Apollo. **His** symbol is a cup of wine

Student B

Work in pairs. Describe the images to your partner. He has to guess the god or goddess.

STRUCTURE BOX

Dionysus is a **young** god. He has got **curly hair**. He is **younger / more intelligent than** Apollo. **His** symbol is a cup of wine

Activity 6

Subject	Classical Culture
Outline	Students have to investigate the origin of the weekdays.
Thinking Skills	Analyzing , selecting and summarizing
Language Focus	Special vocabulary about the topic. The past perfect.
Language Skills	Reading and writing
Time	45'
Level	A1
Preparation	The teacher explains that the origin of the weekdays comes from mythology. He hands over a text and asks for reading and underlining the main ideas about the topic. After that, students will have to read a web (provided by the teacher) to increase their information. Finally, students are asked to do the activity.

Steps to follow:

- Present the origin of the weekdays as a mythical fact.
- Hand over a text to the students.

- Learners have to read it and the main ideas should be underlined.
- After reading, provide the students to a web page.
- They have to switch on their computer or laptop.
- Ask them to look for more information.
- When pupils have finished, a brief summary should be written.

Justification: Students will have to deal with a text that will have been adapted at sentence and word level, and have to cope with an original page web. In this activity, students have to prove their autonomous learning and their ability to select information and to summarize it.

Heading:

The weekdays: their name comes from?

Read the text and write a summary explaining the name’s origin of Sunday and Thursday.

You can get more information [here](#).

The Greeks named the days week after the sun, the moon and the five known planets, which **were in turn named** after the gods: Ares, Hermes, Zeus, Aphrodite and Cronus. The Romans **substituted** the Greek gods **for their equivalent gods**: Mars, Mercury, Jupiter, Venus, and Saturn. The Germanic peoples generally substituted **roughly similar gods** for the Roman gods: Tiu, Woden, Thor, Freya, but **did not replace** Saturn.

Text adapted from: <http://www.crowl.org/lawrence/time/days.html>

Activity 7

Subject	Classical Culture
Outline	Students have to create a new god and present it to the classmates.
Thinking Skills	Integrating and inventing
Language Focus	Special vocabulary about the topic. Description language
Language Skills	Writing and speaking
Time	45’
Level	A1
Preparation	The teacher divides the students in different groups of four. He explains that every group has to invent a new god: main characteristics, relationship with the Olympians, power and symbol. When they finish the task, they have to present their creation to the whole class.

Steps to follow:

- Divide the class in groups of four students.
- Explain the task.

- A new god will be created.
- Learners will present their character to the rest of the class.

Justification: This activity is the last of the lesson, so the students have to use their all knowledge about the topic to create their own character. At the same time, they have to cope with a level of language that proves that they have achieved the linguistic structures and the new vocabulary.

Heading:

In groups create a new god: main characteristics, relationship with the Olympians, power and symbol. Present your invention to your classmates.

Reinforcement

Activity 8

Subject	Classical Culture
Outline	Students have to complete a text with the correct words
Thinking Skills	Solving
Language Focus	Special vocabulary about the topic. Passive voice and present simple
Language Skills	Reading and writing
Time	15'
Level	A1
Preparation	For this activity is needed a laptop or a computer. The teacher will make a text game play with educaplay and will ask students to connect and solve the quiz.

Steps to follow:

- Say the pupils they are going to complete a text about the topic's specific vocabulary.
- Students switch on their computers or laptop.
- The page web is indicated to the learners.
- The quiz will be solved.

Justification: A higher level of language is needed in this activity, due to the passive voice and the third person –s of the present simple. We are to take advantage of a game to foster the learning process, while students are applying their previous knowledge by solving the text.

Heading:

Go to the [web page](#) and fill in the gaps with the correct word.

Activity 9

Subject	Classical Culture
Outline	Students have to make a quizlet
Thinking Skills	Applying and creating
Language Focus	Special vocabulary about the topic.
Language Skills	Writing
Time	45'
Level	A1
Preparation	The teacher explains what a quizlet is and how to make one using this app .

Steps to follow:

- Explain the pupils they are going to create a quizlet
- Students switch on their computers or laptop.
- The page web is indicated to the learners.
- Present a quizlet example.
- Laerners will make their own quizlet.

Justification: This activity is used to do a review of the content and the language, and to encourage learners for the next lesson.

Heading: With the information about the gods make a quizlet. Remember that you have to include an image, the god's name, his power, his symbol and his relationship. (Follow the [example](#))

Conclusion

Throughout this lesson, we suppose that students who chose this subject would be able to understand the topic and learn autonomously, even studying it in a foreign language. We are under the impression that we would have engaged them because the topic has been graded in order to increase the difficulty, and at the same time we used different tools to help students reach a communicative level according to their course.

Also, the Bloom's taxonomy has been used to plan the different activities. We tried to design these by following the thinking skills what is supposed that our students should have achieved at the end of the unit, in order to reach the top of the pyramid. It can be seen at the next figure:

At the same time, we seek that the relationship between language and content developed during the lesson is related to the Cummins matrix, because our aim was that our students are be able to go from the third quadrant (Low Linguistic Demands + High Cognitive Demands) to the fourth one (High Cognitive Demands + High Linguistic Demand)

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